

DIELECTRIC ELASTOMERS MEMBRANE ACTUATOR UNDERGOING POLARIZATION SATURATION

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1 General Introduction

Dielectric elastomers (DEs), a type of electroactive polymer (EAP). The acrylic acid and silicone are common dielectric elastomer materials. Subject to a voltage through its thickness, a membrane of a dielectric elastomer reduces thickness and enlarges area. It was discovered a decade ago that an applied voltage may cause dielectric elastomers to strain over 100% [1]. Because of this large strain, dielectric elastomers are often called artificial muscles. In addition to large voltage-induced strains, other desirable attributes of dielectric elastomers include fast response, high energy density, no noise, light weight, high efficiency and high responsive speed and low cost. This electromechanical coupling is being studied intensely for diverse applications, including soft robots, adaptive optics, Braille display medical devices, and electric generators. The research on dielectric elastomers' failure, large deformation and nonlinear electromechanical stability is an interesting topic in recent years [2-5]. Recently, a lot of research work focused on either large deformation or electromechanical stability has been carried out.

Zhao and Suo proposed a theoretical method to investigate the electromechanical instability of ideal dielectric elastomers [5]. In the statement of this theory, other researchers started to investigate the electromechanical stability of various types of dielectric elastomer combining the strain energy function for hyperelastic materials such as Ogden model, Neo-Hookean model, Arruda-Boyce model and Mooney-Rivlin model. From these researches, the relations among the nominal stress, the pre-stretch, the nominal electric displacement and the nominal electric field were described accurately.

In the above-mentioned theoretical study of dielectric elastomers, linear electrostatic free energy has been employed to characterize the polarization, actuation and instability. This linearity is applicable previously because the conventional dielectric elastomer is susceptible to electromechanical instability, a constant voltage squeezing the elastomer, resulting in a higher electric field and hence ceaselessly thinning the film until failure, and the polarization at electromechanical instability still resides within the linear regime.

In this paper, a free energy function which consists of nonlinear elastic strain energy and nonlinear electric field energy is proposed to construct the constitutive equation and predicate the electromechanical instability and the snap-through instability of dielectric elastomer undergoing polarization saturation.

2 Free energy of dielectric elastomer

A schematic representation of dielectric elastomer is shown in [Figure 1](#). Generally, due to the fact that dielectric elastomer need to work under a certain electric field, a pair of compliant electrodes made of carbon grease are attached on both surfaces of a thin dielectric elastomer film. Both the mechanical stiffness and electrical resistance can be neglected. As shown is [Figure 1](#), in the reference state, the elastomer has an initial dimensions of L_1 , L_2 and L_3 and is subject to zero force and voltage. While in the current state, with the applied forces F_1 , F_2 and F_3 , and voltage U , the elastomer's dimensions deforms to l_1 , l_2 and l_3 and the accumulated charges generated on the electrodes are $+Q$, $-Q$ respectively.

Fig. 1. a membrane of a dielectric elastomer is sandwiched between two compliant electrodes. (a) In the reference state, the dielectric is subject to neither forces nor voltage. (b) In the current state, subject to forces and voltage, the membrane deforms, and charge flows from one electrode to the other through the external conducting wire. Reprinted with permission from Reference 5.

As the dimensions of the elastomer change by δl_1 , δl_2 and δl_3 , therefore, the work done by the forces is $F_1\delta l_1 + F_2\delta l_2 + F_3\delta l_3$. Meanwhile, the work done by the voltage is $U\delta Q$ assuming that charges in amount of δQ flows through the thin film. When the dielectric elastomer is in an equilibrium state of mechanical forces and electrical voltage, the increase in the free energy should be equal to the total work,

$$\delta H = F_1\delta l_1 + F_2\delta l_2 + F_3\delta l_3 + U\delta Q \quad (1)$$

Here H is the Helmholtz free energy of such a thermodynamic system. In a Cartesian coordinate system, the elastomer's stretches in the three direction are defined as: $\lambda_1 = l_1/L_1$, $\lambda_2 = l_2/L_2$ and $\lambda_3 = l_3/L_3$. The nominal stresses s_1 , s_2 , and s_3 are defined by dividing the pre-stretch forces by the area before deformation, i.e., $s_1 = F_1/(l_2l_3)$, $s_2 = F_2/(l_1l_3)$ and $s_3 = F_3/(l_1l_2)$. Similarly, the nominal electric field can be defined as $E^- = U/L_3$ and the nominal electrical displacement as $D^- = Q/(L_1L_2)$. The nominal density of the Helmholtz free energy is defined as $W = H/(L_1L_2L_3)$. Furthermore, define the true stresses by $\sigma_1 = F_1/(\lambda_2\lambda_3L_2L_3)$, $\sigma_2 = F_2/(\lambda_1\lambda_3L_1L_3)$, $\sigma_3 = F_3/(\lambda_1\lambda_2L_1L_2)$, the true

electric field by $E = U/(\lambda_3L_3)$, and the true electric displacement by $D = Q/(\lambda_1\lambda_2L_1L_2)$.

The condition of equilibrium (1) holds in any current state. Based on the above definitions, the small change of the Helmholtz free energy density is expressed as:

$$\delta W = s_1\delta\lambda_1 + s_2\delta\lambda_2 + s_3\delta\lambda_3 + E^- \delta D^- \quad (2)$$

This equilibrium condition will hold for arbitrary small variations of the four independent variables, λ_1 , λ_2 , λ_3 and D^- . Neglecting the variation of temperature, to characterize the dielectric elastomer, the nominal density of the Helmholtz free energy is prescribed as a function of the four independent variables,

$$W = W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-) \quad (3)$$

Under the coupling effect of electric and mechanical fields, the small variation of the four independent variables are $d\lambda_1, d\lambda_2, d\lambda_3$, and dD^- respectively.

The variation of free energy of dielectric elastomer's electromechanical coupling system can be expressed as following

$$\begin{aligned} \delta W = & \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_1} \delta \lambda_1 + \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_2} \delta \lambda_2 + \\ & \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_3} \delta \lambda_3 + \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial D^-} \delta D^- \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Inserting Eq. (4) into Eq. (2), then we can obtain a thermodynamic equilibrium equation in form of,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_1} - s_1 \right] \delta \lambda_1 + \left[\frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_2} - s_2 \right] \delta \lambda_2 + \\ & \left[\frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_3} - s_3 \right] \delta \lambda_3 + \left[\frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial D^-} - E^- \right] \delta D^- = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

This condition of equilibrium holds for any small variations of the four independent variables. Consequently, when the dielectric elastomer is in equilibrium with the applied forces and the applied voltage, the coefficient in front of the variation of each independent variable vanishes, giving,

$$s_1 = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_1} \quad (6)$$

$$s_2 = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_2} \quad (7)$$

$$s_3 = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_3} \quad (8)$$

$$E^- = \frac{\partial W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial D^-} \quad (9)$$

3 Dielectric elastomers undergoing polarization saturation

In a dielectric elastomer membrane actuator, each polymer chain may consist of monomers of electric dipoles. In the absence of the applied voltage, the dipoles undergo thermal fluctuation, and are randomly oriented. The situation is similar to water molecules. When the dielectric elastomer membrane actuator is subject to a voltage, the dipoles rotate toward the direction of the electric field. When the voltage becomes sufficiently high, the dipoles become perfectly aligned with the electric field, and the polarization of the material saturate (Fig. 2). This paper develops a thermodynamic model of dielectric elastomers membrane actuator undergoing polarization saturation. Our model couples this nonlinear dielectric behavior with nonlinear elastic behavior. We obtain an analytical solution of the constitutive equation of dielectric elastomer undergoing polarization saturation, and investigate electromechanical instability. We show that the electromechanical instability is markedly affected by the polarization saturation of dipoles. The model may guide the search for high-performance dielectric elastomer membrane actuator.

Fig. 2. polarization saturation of dielectric elastomers. Reprinted with permission from Reference 5.

4 A special electric energy

An elastomer is a three-dimensional network of long and flexible polymer chains, held together by crosslinks. Each polymer chain consists of such a large number of monomers that the crosslinks affect polarization of the monomers negligibly. That is, the elastomer can polarize nearly as freely as a polymer melt. As an idealization, we may assume that the dielectric behavior of an elastomer is exactly the same as that of a polymer melt, so that the relation between the electric field is a function of the electric displacement independent of deformation:

$$E = f(D) \quad (10)$$

To obtain the special electric field energy, we consider the nonlinear dielectric behavior of a dielectric elastomer. According to Eq. (10), for example, we get the expression of the true electric field and the true electric displacement of dielectric elastomers undergoing polarization saturation as follows

$$E = \frac{D_s}{2\epsilon} \log\left(\frac{1+D/D_s}{1-D/D_s}\right) \quad (11)$$

Here D_s is the saturated electric displacement, E_s is a characteristic electric field. When E is small, D is linearly proportional to E , recovers the linear dielectric behavior. When E is high enough, dielectric elastomer is in the state of polarization saturation, $D \rightarrow D_s$. We obtain the special electric energy of dielectric elastomer,

$$V(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-) = \frac{D_s D^- \lambda_3}{2\epsilon} \log\left(\frac{1+D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}{1-D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}\right) + \frac{D_s^2 \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3}{2\epsilon} \log\left(1 - \frac{D_s^{-2} \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2}}{D_s^2}\right) \quad (12)$$

The nominal stress of dielectric elastomer's thermodynamic system in the three planar principal directions, the nominal electric field in the thickness direction are obtained respectively, as is shown in the followings

$$s_1 = \frac{\partial U(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_1} + \frac{D_s^2}{2\epsilon} \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \log\left(1 - \frac{D_s^{-2} \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2}}{D_s^2}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$s_2 = \frac{\partial U(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_2} + \frac{D_s^2}{2\varepsilon} \lambda_1 \lambda_3 \log\left(1 - \frac{D^- \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2}}{D_s^2}\right) \quad (14)$$

$$s_3 = \frac{\partial U(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, D^-)}{\partial \lambda_3} + \frac{D_s^2}{2\varepsilon} \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \log\left(1 - \frac{D^- \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2}}{D_s^2}\right) + \frac{D_s D^-}{2\varepsilon} \log\left(\frac{1 + D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}{1 - D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}\right) \quad (15)$$

$$E^- = \frac{D_s \lambda_3}{2\varepsilon} \log\left(\frac{1 + D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}{1 - D^- \lambda_1^{-1} \lambda_2^{-1} / D_s}\right) \quad (16)$$

5 Electromechanical stability and snap-through stability

We now investigate an effect of the strain-stiffening on the electromechanical stability and the snap stability of Gent type dielectric elastomer undergoing the polarization saturation. Consider the unequal-biaxial condition of dielectric elastomer, $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda$, we get that

$$\frac{s}{\mu} = \frac{2J_{\text{lim}}}{J_{\text{lim}} - (2\lambda^2 + \lambda^{-4} - 3)} (\lambda - \lambda^{-5}) - \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \frac{D^- \lambda^{-3}}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \log\left(\frac{1 + \frac{D^- \lambda^{-2}}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}}}{1 - \frac{D^- \lambda^{-2}}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}}}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{s}{\mu} = \frac{2J_{\text{lim}}}{J_{\text{lim}} - (2\lambda^2 + \lambda^{-4} - 3)} (\lambda - \lambda^{-5}) - \frac{2D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \left[\frac{\exp\left(2 \frac{E^-}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \lambda^2 \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}}\right) - 1}{\exp\left(2 \frac{E^-}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \lambda^2 \frac{D_s}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}}\right) + 1} \right] \frac{E^-}{\sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}} \lambda \quad (18)$$

And the voltage-stretch curve with different extension limit is showed in Figure 3. When J_{lim} and $D_s / \sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon}$ are both small, the nominal electric field increases monotonously with the stretch, avoiding local maximum value and the dielectric elastomer can approach its stable state. When $D_s / \sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon} \rightarrow \infty$ and J_{lim} is a finite value, the nominal electric field attains the local maximum value first. Then, the dielectric elastomer goes through the snap instability with the voltage

increasing. When $J_{\text{lim}} \rightarrow \infty$ and $D_s / \sqrt{C_1 \varepsilon} \rightarrow \infty$, the dielectric elastomer undergoes the pull-in electromechanical instability. Therefore, to get a large deformation, the applied voltage should achieve two limites, lower than the breakdown voltage of the material, and approaching the voltage undergoing the snap instability.

Fig. 3. consider the effect of the strain-stiffening, nominal electric field and stretch of dielectric elastomer undergoing polarization saturation under the loading condition $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda$.

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